

Drone for Disaster Management

Manikeshwari A
Dept. Computer Science & Engineering
(Business System)
Dayanada Sagar College of
Engineering
Bengaluru, India
1ds23cb020@dsce.edu.in

Ms. Sanjana M Najaraj
Dept. . Computer Science &
Engineering (Business System)
Dayanada Sagar College of
Engineering
Bengaluru, India
sanjanamnagaraj@gmail.com

Abstract— Natural and man-made disaster often result in complete breakdown of communication infrastructure. It causes serious challenges to rescue teams for performing rescue operations. To address this issue, this paper presents a low-cost flight controller using an Arduino Uno R3. It uses a gyroscope and accelerometer integrated module for stability. A four channel RF transmitter receiver module is used to control the quadcopter. The flight controller is integrated with LoRa module which is used to trigger a recorder mounted on the quadcopter. This system can help guide and alert people during times of distress. LoRa is a wireless technology that consumes low power, and has a range around 5-10 km.

Keywords—Arduino, LoRa SX1278, disaster management, MPU6050, ESC, UAV, sensor integration, scalable system.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the development and deployment of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have revolutionised various sectors, ranging from agriculture and logistics to defence and environmental monitoring. UAVs, commonly referred to as drones are aerial platforms capable of flight without a human pilot onboard, typically guided by remote control or onboard microcontrollers. Their advantages include reduced operational risk, low-cost maintenance, the ability to access remote or hazardous areas, and rapid deployment, all of which make them increasingly important in both civilian and military contexts. One particularly critical domain where UAVs have demonstrated transformative potential is in disaster management. Natural and man-made disasters such as earthquakes, floods, wildfires, and building collapses often result in highly unstable and inaccessible environments, complicating efforts by first responders to assess the situation, locate victims, and deliver aid. In such scenarios, UAVs can serve as the first line of aerial reconnaissance. The primary objective of the system is to alert and guide people during disaster situations where conventional communication and navigation systems may be unavailable.

Quadcopter is a type of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) which uses four motors and propellers to produce thrust for flight. The movement of the drone are categorised into four parts- roll, pitch yaw and throttle. Speeds of the four motors are varied through the electronic speed controllers (ESCs) to achieve these movements. A gyroscope which is mounted on the quadcopter measures the roll, pitch and yaw values as the position of the quadcopter changes. These values are compared and once the difference between the measured value and the input signal is identified, the speeds of the motors are varied to adjust the quadcopter. This increases precision and improves stability of the quadcopter.

LoRa (Long Range) is a low-power wide-area network (LPWAN) modulation scheme developed by Semtech, based on Chirp Spread Spectrum (CSS) modulation. It operates in unlicensed sub-GHz ISM bands such as 433 MHz, 868 MHz, and 915 MHz, achieving long-range communication with high

sensitivity (−137 dBm to −149 dBm) and data rates between 0.3 kbps and 50 kbps. Key parameters include spreading factor (SF7 to SF12), bandwidth (125 to 500 kHz), and coding rate allow flexible trade-offs between range, robustness, and energy efficiency. The SX1278 is a LoRa transceiver optimised for 433 MHz operation. It offers high link budget performance with up to +20 dBm output power and −148 dBm sensitivity, while consuming only 9.9 mA in receive mode and 29 mA during transmit at +10 dBm [5],[6]. Its SPI interface, built-in CRC, forward error correction, and programmable preamble support make it well-suited for integration with Arduino Uno microcontroller. The proposed system utilizes the SX1278 LoRa module with Arduino Uno boards to establish point-to-point wireless communication. A push-button on the transmitter node initiates the transmission of a predefined message using the 433 MHz LoRa band. Upon reception, the receiver node activates an ISD1820 voice playback module, which plays a pre-recorded audio message.

Section II talks about literature survey. Section III and IV are about the design and working of the system. Section V contains information about the results we have obtained and section IV is the conclusion

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and Low-Power Wide Area Network (LPWAN) technologies such as LoRa have gained considerable attention in recent years for their potential applications in disaster response and communication. The design of stable and responsive flight controllers is fundamental to UAV operation. Ömürlü and Gürkan [1] presented a comprehensive STM32F407VG-based quadrotor controller integrating IMU sensors (gyroscope, accelerometer, magnetometer, barometer, GPS) and implemented sensor fusion using Kalman filters. Their controller supported both manual and autonomous flight with telemetry integration and demonstrated stable performance in real flight tests. While STM32-based solutions offer robustness, several studies have explored simpler platforms. For instance, Ji and Turkoglu [3] developed an Arduino-based quadcopter focusing on educational use and experimental PID tuning. Ghosh et al. [2] also explored a low-cost Arduino-based UAV, validating its effectiveness in basic stabilisation and flight control, making it suitable for lightweight mission-specific applications.

LoRa, operating on Chirp Spread Spectrum (CSS), has emerged as a viable LPWAN solution for long-range, low-power communication. Turčinović et al. [5] conducted real-world measurements of over 6,500 LoRa messages to evaluate the effect of spreading factor (SF) on RSSI, SNR, and time-on-air (ToA). Their results demonstrated that higher SFs significantly increase coverage but also elevate ToA and energy consumption, highlighting the trade-off between range and efficiency.

LoRa's use in emergency response contexts has been further explored through voice transmission applications.

Kagai et al. [4] designed a Voice-over-LoRa (VLoRa) system capable of transmitting compressed voice data over LoRa links using Codec 2. Their system successfully transmitted intelligible audio across distances exceeding 1 km, demonstrating the feasibility of infrastructure-free communication in disaster-stricken regions. The study also highlighted the importance of packet sizing, noting that larger packets improved audio quality but increased packet loss rates.

While our current system focuses on broadcasting pre-recorded audio messages, future work could extend this design to incorporate real-time voice communication using similar techniques, and hence enable two-way voice-based interaction in disaster zones. Building on this, the proposed system can be further enhanced by incorporating real-time voice streaming protocols such as Codec 2 to support two-way communication in future iterations.

III. DESIGN OF QUADCOPTER

Figure. 1 Block diagram of flight controller and LoRa communication

A. Arduino Uno R3 (ATMEGA328P)

Acts as the primary flight controller and system processor. Operating at 16 MHz with 2 KB SRAM and 32 KB flash memory, the Arduino Uno provides sufficient resources for a basic flight controller. All firmware logic for sensor interfacing and motor control is developed using this platform. The flight controller Arduino receives PWM signals from the receiver and decimal values from the gyroscope. It compares the two values and sends PWM signals to the electronic speed controllers (ESCs). Another Arduino is mounted on the drone which is connected to a LoRa SX128 module and a ISD1820 voice recorder and player module. When a trigger signal is received via the LoRa module, the Arduino triggers the recorded message on the ISD1820 module.

B. MPU6050 (3-AXIS GYROSCOPE + 3-AXIS ACCELEROMETER)

A 6-DOF (degrees of freedom) Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) used to detect the drone's angular velocity and linear acceleration. It communicates with the Arduino Uno via the I2C protocol (SCL, SDA), providing orientation data.

C. SPEED CONTROLLERS (ESCS, 30A)

Each ESC converts the PWM signal from the Arduino into three-phase AC signals to control a brushless motor. ESCs take power from a LiPo battery (11.1V) and regulate the motor's speed and direction.

D. BRUSHLESS DC MOTORS (1000 KV)

These three-phase motors are driven by ESCs and provide the lift required for flight. The motor's KV rating determines

the number of revolutions per minute (RPM) per volt applied. Four motors are used in a quadcopter configuration (two clockwise and two counterclockwise) to balance torque and maintain stability.

E. QUADCOPTER FRAME (X-CONFIGURATION)

Constructed from reinforced plastic, the frame houses the motors, flight controller, ESCs, battery, and payload. The symmetrical X-configuration allows uniform thrust distribution and simplified control logic. F450 drone frame is used in this project.

F. PROPELLERS (SIZE: 10")

Attached directly to the motor shafts, the propellers generate thrust based on their rotational speed. The combination of clockwise and counterclockwise propellers is critical for cancelling out yaw-inducing torque. Propeller selection is based on motor specifications, thrust requirements, and payload weight.

G. LORA SX1278 MODULE (433MHZ, SPI INTERFACE)

The LoRa SX1278 module enables long-range wireless communication using the 433 MHz ISM band. SX128 is a transceiver module. LoRa module at the user's side is configured to work as transmitter and the one on the drone is configured to work as receiver. The trigger button is connected to the system as shown in Figure 1.

H. ISD1820 VOICE PLAYBACK MODULE (SPEAKER & MICROPHONE)

This module includes a built-in microphone for recording short messages (up to 20 seconds) and a speaker for playback. It is controlled using GPIO pins from the Arduino. The playback can be triggered via code.

I. RF TRANSMITTER AND RECEIVER MODULE FSCT6B (MODE 2, 2.4 GHZ)

Provides manual control input for the drone using a handheld remote. The receiver module interfaces with the Arduino Uno via PWM signal lines, allowing real-time control of throttle, pitch, roll, and yaw. The module itself has 6 channels but only 4 channels are used due to simple design

IV. WORKING OF THE SYSTEM

The following sub-headings show the working of the flight controller. Working principle of quadcopter Roll refers to the leftward and rightward tilt of the quadcopter. The difference in speed of the right and left side motors help achieve the required roll. Pitch refers to forward and backward tilt of the quadcopter. Forward tilt along with thrust helps achieve

forward movement of the UAV. Difference in speeds of the motors at the front and the back are used to achieve this. Turning towards the left or right determines the yaw value. By increasing the speed of motors on opposite sides includes rotational torque without creating additional thrust. This mechanism is used to turn the quadcopter [2]. Hence a four-channel transmitter can be used to control the quadcopter. The roll, pitch and yaw orientations are as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Roll, Pitch and Yaw Directions of Drone [7]

A. Gyroscope and Accelerometer data

The Arduino continuously communicates with the MPU6050 sensor via the I2C protocol to read real-time data on the gyroscope to measure angular velocity (degrees/seconds) along the X, Y, and Z axes and the accelerometer to measure linear acceleration (m/s^2) on all three axes. This raw data is used to determine the drone's orientation of pitch, roll, and yaw. The collected data is filtered to reduce noise and estimate the current tilt angles of the drone. This processed information is used to detect any deviation from the desired level position.

B. Motor Control Logic

Based on the orientation data, the Arduino adjusts the speed of each motor through PWM signals sent to the Electronic Speed Controllers. If the drone tilts forward (pitch), the rear motors are sped up to push it back level. If it rolls left, the right motors are sped up to correct the tilt. Yaw is controlled by varying the torque generated by clockwise and counterclockwise motors. This real-time adjustment keeps the drone stable in the air and allows it to respond to movement commands.

C. Manual or Remote Commands

Control signals from an RF receiver (transmitter-operated) are read via PWM inputs. These signals define desired throttle, pitch, roll, and yaw. The Arduino combines these commands with sensor data to adjust motor speeds accordingly.

D. LORA RECEIVER WORKING

The LoRa module listens for incoming packets which contain a short, predefined strings which are sent from the transmitter's side when the trigger button is pressed. The Arduino compares the received command with known values to decide what action to take.

E. TRIGGERING THE ISD1820 MODULE

When a matching command is received, the Arduino sends a digital HIGH signal to the PLAY pin of the ISD1820. The ISD1820 then plays the pre-recorded message stored in its internal memory. The module has an onboard microphone and speaker for recording and playback, or an external speaker can be used for louder output.

F. FUTURE WORK

The current model uses a module which can only play recorded messages to convey instructions to disaster-stricken areas. This can be extended such that audio signals can be sent to the drone in real-time [4].

V. RESULTS

The proposed disaster-alert UAV system was evaluated through comprehensive testing of its two primary subsystems: (a) the flight controller for quadcopter stability and control, and (b) the LoRa-based communication module for remote

alert transmission. The integration of both systems was also validated through real-world scenario simulations.

A. Flight Controller Evaluation

The flight controller was implemented using an Arduino-based platform interfaced with an MPU6050 IMU sensor. A PID control loop was developed to stabilise the quadcopter in roll, pitch, and yaw axes by regulating motor speeds via Electronic Speed Controllers (ESCs). The following observations were made:

Figure 3. Flight Controller Mounted on Quadcopter

1) *Hover Stability:* The system maintained stable hovering with an average deviation of $\pm 4^\circ$ in both roll and pitch, under mild environmental disturbances.

2) *Control Response:* User-defined input commands (simulated RC signals) resulted in accurate directional manoeuvres with minimal overshoot.

3) *Payload Capacity:* The drone successfully carried the full payload—including the LoRa module and ISD1820 voice alert circuit—totalling approximately 250 g, without compromising lift or stability.

4) *Flight Duration:* The average flight time was recorded at 6–7 minutes using a standard 3S 11.1V 2200mAh LiPo battery, which met operational expectations for short-duration deployments.

B. LoRa Communication Performance

Point-to-point communication between two Arduino Uno boards was established using SX1278 LoRa modules operating at 433 MHz. A push-button was used to initiate transmission of a predefined message from the transmitter node, while the receiver activated an ISD1820 module to play a pre-recorded audio alert.

1) *Transmission Accuracy:* The system achieved 99% successful transmission rate within tested ranges.

2) *Range Testing:* In open-line-of-sight conditions, reliable communication was achieved. In partially obstructed urban areas, the range decreased slightly.

3) *Audio Trigger Response:* The time delay between transmission and playback was near-instantaneous.

4) *Power Consumption: Each node operated continuously for over five hours on a 9 V battery, confirming the suitability of the system for extended deployment.*

Figure 4. Testing of LoRa SX1278

C. Integrated System Testing

Figure 5 Testing of Quadcopter

Final validation was carried out with both subsystems operating simultaneously onboard the UAV. During test flights, the LoRa module was triggered from airborne positions to simulate alert generation in a disaster scenario. The LoRa module's operation did not interfere with the flight control system. Both SPI-based communication and PWM-based motor control operated concurrently without signal corruption. The results demonstrate that the integrated UAV system is capable of delivering stable flight performance while reliably transmitting disaster alerts via LoRa in low-infrastructure environments.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a drone-based communication system using LoRa technology for effective communication where there is complete blackout. LoRa consumes low power and is used for long range communication. The experimental result showed that system works well in sending emergency messages. As it uses low power, which makes it suitable for long time operations in disaster zone. Because of its low-cost flight controller and easy to set up, this solution is helpful in places with uneven terrain. In future, the system can be improved by integrating the facility of real-time communication, delivering first aids and medicines to survivors and making drone more autonomous for better performance during natural or man-made disasters

REFERENCES

[1] V. E. Ömürlü and B. Gurkan, "STM32F407VG Microprocessor Based Flight Controller Design Experimented on a Quadrotor," 2019 6th

International Conference on Electrical and Electronics Engineering (ICEEE), Istanbul, Turkey, 2019, pp. 302-306

[2] Ghosh, A., Roy, H., & Dhar, S. (2018). "Arduino Quadcopter." Fourth International Conference on Research in Computational Intelligence and Communication Networks (ICRCICN), pp. 280–283.

[3] [7] Ji, A., & Turkoglu, E. (2015). "Development of a low-cost experimental quadcopter testbed using an Arduino controller and software." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1508.07836*.

[4] F. Kagai, P. Branch, J. But and R. Allen, "Voice Over LoRa™," 2024 International Conference on Information Networking (ICOIN), Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, pp. 526-531

[5] F. Turčinović, J. Vuković, S. Božo and G. Šišul, "Analysis of LoRa Parameters in Real-World Communication," 2020 International Symposium ELMAR, Zadar, Croatia, 2020, pp. 87-90

[6] Semtech Corporation, "SX1278/79 Long Range Low Power Transceiver IC," Datasheet, Rev. 3.0, Apr. 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.semtech.com/uploads/documents/sx1278_79.pdf

[7] A. Bajaj, M. Arora, M. Singh and R. Kumar, "Performance Evaluation of AR Drone as an Autonomous Agent in Search and Rescue Missions," 2018 IEEE International Conference on Advanced Networks and Telecommunications Systems (ANTS), Indore, India, 2018, pp. 1-6.

[8] R. S. Benatti, C. P. de Souza and O. Baiocchi, "An Optimization Method based on LoRa Parameters for Energy Consumption Reduction," 2021 5th International Symposium on Instrumentation Systems, Circuits and Transducers (INSCIT), Campinas, Brazil, 2021, pp. 1-5,

[9] T. Tin Toong, S. Yogarayan, S. Fatimah Abdul Razak, A. Ee Mae, A. Azman and K. Rama, "Analyzing the Performance of LoRa Using SX1278 and Dragino Module," 2024 12th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT), Bandung, Indonesia, 2024, pp. 347-353

[10] P. Gupta, F. Ambrose, S. Naik, M. Tanki, A. Kumbhar and J. Shah, "STM32 Based Quadcopter For Obstacle Avoidance Using Ultrasonic Sensor," 2023 6th International Conference on Advances in Science and Technology (ICAST), Mumbai, India, 2023, pp. 122-126

[11] B. Sumantri, N. Tamami, Y. B. Nuraga and B. Kurniawan, "Development of a Low-Cost Embedded Flight Controller for Quadcopter," 2020 International Electronics Symposium (IES), Surabaya, Indonesia, 2020, pp. 233-238

[12] Z. J. R. Kamoona and M. Ilyas, "Investigating the Performance of LoRa Communication for Nominal LoRa and Interleaved Chirp Spreading LoRa," 2022 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence of Things (ICAIoT), Istanbul, Turkey, 2022, pp. 1-7

[13] B. P. R. Bhavanam and P. Ragam, "Exploring LoRa Signal Propagation in Indoor and Outdoor Environments: A Comparative Study," 2024 IEEE International Conference on Smart Power Control and Renewable Energy (ICSPCRE), Rourkela, India, 2024, pp. 1-6,

[14] R. Khandait, V. Kumar, V. Bhurse, V. Tiwari and S. Khubalkar, "Quadcopter Control using Different Controllers," 2022 International Conference on Intelligent Controller and Computing for Smart Power (ICICCS), Hyderabad, India, 2022, pp. 1-6

[15] A. Kaba, A. Ermeydan and E. Kiyak, "Model derivation, attitude control and Kalman filter estimation of a quadcopter," 2017 4th International Conference on Electrical and Electronic Engineering (ICEEE), Ankara, Turkey, 2017, pp. 210-214

[16] S. Dutta and A. Ghosh, "DisasChat: An End-to-End Encrypted Off-Grid LoRa-Based Smartphone Communication System for Disaster and Crisis Scenarios," 2022 IEEE 19th India Council International Conference (INDICON), Kochi, India, 2022, pp. 1-6